

Investigation of Reaction Kinetics of the Selective Hydrogenation of a Terminal Alkyne under Industrially Relevant Conditions with Benchtop NMR Spectroscopy

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Keywords

Hydrogenation Kinetics, Terminal Alkynes, Multiphase Reaction Monitoring, Applied qNMR, Online qNMR, Process Monitoring, QM-qNMR, High Pressure Benchtop NMR

Abstract

Heterogeneously catalyzed hydrogenations are pivotal in the chemical industry. Studying these reactions often demands significant experimental effort due to safety requirements, elevated pressures and temperatures, and the operational modes of traditional laboratory reactors. To address these challenges, we propose an automated, efficient and cost-effective method for characterizing such reactions within a kinetic laboratory setting. Utilizing benchtop NMR as a non-invasive, automatable analytical tool offers advantages in terms of space and cost over high-frequency NMR, though its limited spectral resolution may restrict applicability to certain reaction systems. In this study, we investigate the hydrogenation of 2-methyl-3-butyn-2-ol (MBY) to 2-methyl-3-buten-2-ol (MBE) as a model reaction. While literature provides extensive data on the main components, the formation of side-products remains inadequately explained. Conducting the reaction in a batch reactor, we assess the detection and quantification of side-products. Samples withdrawn during hydrogenation are analyzed using benchtop NMR coupled with a quantum mechanical Bayesian quantitative NMR analysis, employing component knowledge to quantify mixtures through mathematical modeling. We collect kinetic data, gaining both qualitative and quantitative insights into the reaction network at temperatures up to 80 °C and a pressure of 10 bar. Our findings demonstrate that the reaction mixture's composition can be quantitatively monitored in real-time, facilitating the derivation of kinetic parameters. Despite the minor formation of various side-products, we successfully quantify dimeric reaction products and evaluate process parameters influencing their formation. The integration of a reactor, online benchtop NMR, and advanced qNMR data analysis yields high-quality results essential for process optimization.

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1 Introduction

Reliable information on reaction kinetics is imperative for engineers to facilitate model-based design, scale-up, and optimization of the reactor and process conditions, as well as for safety considerations [1]. To mitigate the uncertainty of model predictions, kinetic data must be collected and thoroughly studied in the laboratory under conditions that closely resemble the anticipated conditions in industrial reactors. To facilitate studies of heterogeneous catalysis, particularly in gas-liquid reactions such as hydrogenation, a specialized laboratory reactor system is necessary. The system must be capable of safe operation under industrially relevant hydrogenation conditions, typically up to 100 °C and 20 bar of hydrogen pressure, as required for alkynol hydrogenations.

Furthermore, real industrial feedstocks and reaction mixtures (e.g., without solvents) with immobilized solid catalyst must be applicable. In addition to a suitable reactor vessel, high sampling rates are required to obtain the full kinetic information of the reaction, while at the same time the sampling must not interfere with the process [2]. In particular, inline optical spectroscopy (e.g., infrared (IR) or Raman spectroscopy) has been employed extensively for analyzing reaction processes [3–6]. In conjunction with fiber probes, process analysis can be conducted directly inside the reactor (inline). Using a sample loop and a flow cell, the analysis can be performed online. However, a notable disadvantage of optical spectroscopy lies in its requirement for meticulous calibration prior to quantitative analysis as well as the inability to derive information about unknown components from the analytical data [7]. This limitation restricts its application, particularly in synthesis processes involving complex reaction networks, where the presence of unstable or unknown intermediates or side-products is common.

Consequently, over the past few years, Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (NMR) spectroscopy has emerged as a prominent alternative for reaction analysis [8–21]. The advantage of NMR spectroscopy is twofold: it can be used both for elucidation of unknown species in the reaction network and for quantitative analysis. The latter is required for the development of models of chemical equilibria and reaction kinetics [15].

To address the criteria related to the reactor vessel and the process analysis method, this study utilized a high-pressure stirred gas-liquid tank reactor, wherein the catalyst is immobilized in a basket. The reactor was equipped with a sampling loop. Due to safety concerns, operation of the reactor in a fume hood is required. In this case, benchtop

^1H NMR spectrometers, which utilize solid-state magnets, are more suitable for process analysis than high-frequency spectrometers, which employ cryogenically cooled, superconducting electromagnets. First, the benchtop spectrometer can be positioned in close proximity to the reactor, thereby minimizing the length (and volume, respectively) of the sample loop and ensuring that no sample is transferred outside the fume hood. Additionally, benchtop spectrometers generally incur lower investment and operational costs compared to high-frequency models. No deuterated solvents are needed and the undiluted reaction mixture from a process can directly analyzed. However, benchtop NMR spectrometers feature reduced sensitivity and chemical resolution capabilities when compared to high-frequency devices. Consequently, direct integration of peaks to obtain quantitative spectra is frequently impractical due to significant overlap of peaks and a low signal-to-noise ratio [22]. To address this challenge, numerous mathematical analysis methods have been developed and evaluated, facilitating the quantification of spectra with overlapping peaks and/or low signal-to-noise ratios [23, 24]. Recently, Holland and co-workers have introduced an analysis method that employs a quantum mechanical model (QM) of the species present in the reaction mixture to interpret their NMR spectra (QM-qNMR) [19, 25–30]. Quantitative information of the different species is obtained by fitting the spectral model to the NMR spectra of liquid samples taken from experiments. The fitting procedure provides a reliable estimation of the model parameters (i.e., the relative concentration of the species) using a Bayesian approach that enables an easy incorporation of prior knowledge of the spectra, e.g., information on chemical shifts and J-couplings. As demonstrated in numerous studies, this model-based analysis method has proven effective in generating reliable quantitative data from benchtop ^1H NMR spectra of complex mixtures. This method significantly enhances the capabilities of benchtop ^1H NMR spectroscopy, making it a valuable tool for process analysis [19–21, 25, 30, 31]. The objective of this paper is to illustrate the viability of benchtop NMR spectroscopy in conjunction with the analysis method outlined in the work of Matviychuk *et al.* [27] for the study of heterogeneous catalyst hydrogenation reactions under conditions that are relevant to industry.

The selective hydrogenation of 2-methyl-3-buten-2-ol (MBY) to 2-methyl-3-buten-2-ol (MBE) was selected as the test reaction. The selected heterogeneous hydrogenation reaction serves as a model to demonstrate the efficacy of on-line analysis with benchtop NMR spectroscopy in conjunction with a model-based analysis method as a means to study reactions under industrially relevant conditions. In the industrial context, catalytic hydrogenations of acetylenic alcohols to alkenols are employed to produce a range of fine chemicals and intermediate products [32]. MBE plays a pivotal role in the synthesis of synthetic vitamins A and E, as well as fragrance intermediates and is usually obtained by a partial hydrogenation of MBY typically conducted as a batch-wise process [33]. However, the selectivity of this reaction is diminished by the formation of the undesired

secondary product, 2-methylbutan-2-ol (MBA) due to successive hydrogenation of the double bond. As the separation of MBE and MBA is difficult and side product formation leads to product loss, information on the reaction kinetics and reaction network is important in order to drive the industrial implementation of this reaction towards higher selectivity [33]. The kinetics of the reaction system investigated here have already been studied in several studies [34–36]. The primary objective of these studies was to optimize the catalyst system to achieve high selectivity toward the desired product, MBE. Most authors therefore prioritize examining the kinetics of the primary reaction. Furthermore, the formation of C₁₀ dimeric compounds as byproducts was described in the literature, as cited in [35] and [34].

There is a limited availability of data concerning the reaction network, particularly the formation of those side products undesirable in the industrial process. General hypotheses regarding the formation of dimers from terminal alkynes have been proposed previously, as evidenced by the relevant literature [37–41]. However, the offline collection and analysis of samples using gas chromatography in these studies has hindered the ability to comprehensively elucidate the individual chemical structures and reaction pathways of these dimeric compounds. Consequently, the existing body of knowledge concerning the dimer formation is scarce, and it is necessary to characterize the formed dimers in order to draw conclusions about the most likely formation pathway.

The objective of this study is twofold: firstly, validate the QM-qNMR as a tool to study hydrogenation reactions under industrially relevant conditions yielding main reaction kinetics, and secondly, arising as a complementary finding, suggesting reaction pathways of the formation of dimeric compounds and confirm hypotheses regarding their kinetics. The latter is of particular significance, as it facilitates the optimization of selectivity by altering the behavior of the catalyst or the process conditions.

The objective of this study is therefore twofold: firstly, to examine the kinetics of the primary reaction pathway, specifically from MBY to MBE, and secondly, to suggest reaction pathways for the formation of dimeric side-products and confirm hypotheses regarding their kinetics.

2 The Chemical System

2.1 Chemical Reaction

In the main reaction (I), the alkynol MBY is hydrogenated on a heterogeneous catalyst to the desired product 2-methyl-3-buten-2-ol (MBE), which is further hydrogenated in an undesired subsequent reaction (II) to 2-methylbutan-2-ol (MBA):

Figure 2.1: Catalytic hydrogenation of MBY on a palladium catalyst with hydrogen to form MBE and subsequent reaction to form MBA and potentially produced dimers by reductive dimerization.

Several catalyst materials can be used. Most commonly, the reaction is carried out on a heterogeneous palladium catalyst, as this type of catalyst is known for its high selectivity for the hydrogenation of triple bonds [42]. This type of catalyst was also used in this study. The reaction can be carried out in a batch process at pressures of up to 10 bar and temperatures of up to 80 °C without dilution by solvent [34]. Under these conditions, high selectivities for MBE of up to 97 % have been reported [43]. In addition to the main reaction, the formation of side-products through dimerization is also described in literature. A large number of possible dimerization reactions of terminal alkynes are reported in literature [37–41]. Many of them also occur when palladium-based catalysts are used.

Depending on the catalyst and reaction conditions, different dimers are formed and different reaction pathways are assumed [37–40]. In principle, dimerizations can be divided into oxidative, redox-neutral and reducing reactions [39]. In consideration of the prevailing reaction conditions, a reducing dimerization by reacting two terminal alkynes together with hydrogen is postulated, as shown in Fig. 2.1 for the formation of 2,7-dimethyl-3,5-octadien-2,7-diol and subsequent products [39–41].

2.2 Kinetic and Reactor Model

The kinetic of the stepwise hydrogenation of the alkynol MBY (I) via the alkenol MBE to the alkanol MBA (II) is described as a Langmuir-Hinshelwood mechanism, taking into consideration the reaction of the adsorbed reactants to be the rate-determining step ignoring the dimerization reaction. To describe the rates of the consecutive hydrogenation reactions, Equations (2.1) and (2.2) are applied. For more information on their derivation, please refer to the relevant literature [34, 44].

$$r_{\text{I}} = \frac{a \cdot k_{\text{I}} \cdot K_{\text{MBY}} \cdot K_{\text{H}_2} \cdot c_{\text{MBY}} \cdot c_{\text{H}_2}}{\left(1 + K_{\text{MBY}} \cdot c_{\text{MBY}} + \sqrt{K_{\text{H}_2} \cdot c_{\text{H}_2}} + K_{\text{MBE}} \cdot c_{\text{MBE}} + K_{\text{MBA}} \cdot c_{\text{MBA}}\right)^2} \quad (2.1)$$

$$r_{\text{II}} = \frac{a \cdot k_{\text{II}} \cdot K_{\text{MBE}} \cdot K_{\text{H}_2} \cdot c_{\text{MBE}} \cdot c_{\text{H}_2}}{\left(1 + K_{\text{MBY}} \cdot c_{\text{MBY}} + \sqrt{K_{\text{H}_2} \cdot c_{\text{H}_2}} + K_{\text{MBE}} \cdot c_{\text{MBE}} + K_{\text{MBA}} \cdot c_{\text{MBA}}\right)^2} \quad (2.2)$$

With r_{I} and r_{II} as the rate of reaction (I) or (II), respectively, the corresponding rate constants are k_{I} and k_{II} . K_i is the equilibrium constant of the absorption of species i on the catalyst surface with $i = \{\text{H}_2, \text{MBE}, \text{MBA}, \text{MBY}\}$. c_i denotes the molar concentration of species i in the liquid phase, which is calculated with the liquid mixture's molar volume under reaction conditions.

The molar volume of the liquid phase $v_{\text{mix}}^{(n)}$ was considered to depend on both the temperature and the composition and was approximated as the sum of the pure component's

molar volume, each weighted by its mole fraction neglecting any excess volume [45–48]:

$$v_{\text{mix}}^{(n)}(T) = \sum_{k=1}^{N_{\text{comp}}} v_i^{(n)}(T) \cdot x_i \quad (2.3)$$

It is hypothesized that due to the intensive mixing of the gas and liquid phases within the reactor, the influence of gas-liquid mass transfer on the reaction can be neglected. It is further assumed that the concentration of dissolved hydrogen c_{H_2} is equivalent to that of the phase equilibrium (gas solubility) at the given pressure p and temperature T . A correlation for the solubility of hydrogen in pure MBY was adapted from literature to describe the solubility of hydrogen in the reaction mixture under consideration [49].

$$c_{\text{H}_2} = \frac{p}{H_0 \cdot \exp\left(-\frac{\Delta E}{R \cdot T}\right)} \quad (2.4)$$

To consider the deactivation of catalyst between experiments, expressions (2.1) and (2.2) are equally extended by a deactivation factor a . It represents the decrease of catalytic activity due to aging. It scales between 1 (fresh catalyst) and 0 (catalyst without any activity) and it is modeled as a function of accumulative operating time t_{B} using the empirical correlation presented in (2.5).

$$a = \exp(-k_{\text{des}} \cdot t_{\text{B}}) \quad (2.5)$$

The liquid phase in the reactor is assumed to be ideally mixed. Hence, the temporal change of the concentrations of MBE, MBY and MBA are described by simple batch reactor models:

$$\frac{dc_{\text{MBY}}}{dt} = \frac{n_{\text{Pd}}}{V_1(t)} \cdot r_1 \quad (2.6)$$

$$\frac{dc_{\text{MBE}}}{dt} = \frac{n_{\text{Pd}}}{V_1(t)} \cdot (r_1 - r_2) \quad (2.7)$$

$$\frac{dc_{\text{MBA}}}{dt} = \frac{n_{\text{Pd}}}{V_1(t)} \cdot r_2 \quad (2.8)$$

The change in liquid volume due to sampling is taken into account in cases samples were manually withdrawn from the reactor (see Sec. (3.1)).

$$V_1(t_i) = V_1(t_{i-1}) - V_{\text{sample},i} \quad (2.9)$$

n_{Pd} describes the amount of Pd filled into the reactor. It is calculated using the mass of catalyst and the mass fraction of Pd specified by the supplier.

3 Material and Methods

3.1 Experimental Set-Up and Procedure

The reactor configuration comprised a high-pressure stirred tank reactor vessel with a gross volume of 270 milliliters. The catalyst pellets were positioned within a stainless steel mesh catalyst basket. The stirring process was facilitated by a neodymium magnet stirring rod in conjunction with a laboratory magnetic stir plate, which also functioned as a heater for the reaction setup. Mixing was enhanced by the catalyst basket, which served as a baffle. The reactor was equipped with a PT1000 temperature probe (VWR) for regulating the heater and a Thermocouple (Philips CI 5 D 500/2000) for temperature monitoring. The reactor headspace was equipped with gas valves and a pressure transducer (Siemens Sietrans P220). The process of sampling was facilitated by an expansion valve that was connected to the lowest point of the reactor. A schematic drawing of the reactor configuration is shown in Fig. 3.1.

Figure 3.1: Schematic of the stirred-tank reactor with built-in catalyst basket, magnetic stirrer plate with temperature control, gas supply system and sampling unit.

In the hydrogenation experiments, spherical particles of palladium on aluminum oxide (Al_2O_3) with a mass fraction of 0.5 % palladium and a diameter between 2 and 4 millimeters were utilized as a solid catalyst and were purchased from Thermo Scientific. 0.519 g of the particles were weighed and transferred into the catalyst basket. Voids in the basket were filled with glass beads to prevent the catalyst from floating. The catalyst basket was then screwed into the reactor cover and mounted on the stirred tank container, also in the glovebox under a nitrogen atmosphere. The catalyst remained in the inertized reactor between the experiments. The reactant for the hydrogenation, MBY with a purity of 98 % (m/m) from Thermo Scientific, and hydrogen with a purity of 99.999 % from Air Liquid were used.

To validate the analytical method, reference samples were prepared with the same MBY as for the hydrogenation experiments. For more details, see Section 3.2. Furthermore, MBE with a purity of 98 % (m/m) from Sigma-Aldrich, and MBA with a purity of 99 % (m/m) from Supelco were used for that purpose. An analytical balance (AX205, Mettler Toledo, accuracy 0.03 mg) was used for sample preparation. All liquid chemicals were dried with a 3 Å molecular sieve from Carl Roth. The nitrogen used for inertization was purchased

from NipponGas with a purity of 99.9999 %.

The reactor was equipped with two different options for sampling the reaction mixture: I) manual removal of liquid samples directly from the reaction mixture using a needle valve, and II) semi-continuous delivery of liquid sample volumes through a sample loop to the NMR spectrometer and back into the reactor. The latter option enabled online process analysis (see Fig. 3.1). The sampling loop was made of a 1/16" transparent PFA capillary tubing (IDEX) with an inner diameter of 1 mm allowing any gas bubbles that might affect the measurement to be detected visually. The part of the sample loop that was passed through the benchtop NMR spectrometer consisted of a 1/8" PEEK capillary tubing (IDEX) with an inner diameter of 2 mm. This configuration was selected to maximize the sample volume within the NMR active part of the spectrometer (i.e., the RF coil). This, in turn, maximized the signal-to-noise ratio of the acquired NMR spectra. An additively manufactured centering device ensured the sample loop was positioned vertically and straight in the spectrometer bore. A high-pressure pump (Knauer Smartline 100) was used to convey the liquid through the sample tube.

Prior to the execution of each experiment, the reactor was filled with approximately 100 g corresponding to 120 mL of the reactant MBY. No solvent was used. The filling procedure was terminated by repeatedly flushing the headspace with nitrogen, a process that effectively removes oxygen from the system. Subsequently, the liquid reaction mixture was heated until the desired temperature was attained.

Thereafter, the reactor was flushed with hydrogen by repeated pressurization and depressurization for three times and eventually pressurized with hydrogen to nominal pressure. Pressure was kept constant during the experiment by means of a pressure regulator connected to the hydrogen supply. During the heating phase, the stirrer was not initiated, thereby minimizing mass transfer between the gas phase (hydrogen), liquid phase, and catalyst. This approach ensured minimal reaction yields prior to the start of experiments. Magnetic stirring was initiated to start the reaction. The stirrer speed was maintained constant throughout all experiments. In preliminary experiments, it was ascertained by observing the opened vessel that the selected stirrer type and stirrer speed are adequate to ensure dispersion of gas bubbles in the liquid phase.

The initiation of the experiment (reaction time $t = 0$) was marked by the commencement of the sampling procedure, which entailed the initial analysis of the composition of the reaction mixture. During the experiment, either sampling method I or sampling method II was chosen. Manual sampling (method I) was performed by releasing the reaction mixture directly from the reactor via a needle valve. An initial purge of the pipe segment upstream of the needle valve was performed to remove leftover fluid prior to initiating flow before filling a 5 mm NMR tube (NMR Economy Tube, Wilmad) with the sample. To account for the loss of reaction mixture (or the increase in the ratio of catalyst to re-

action mixture), the mass of the withdrawn liquid was recorded using a balance (PR1203, Mettler Toledo). The online process analysis (method II) was carried out using semi-continuous automated stop-flow measurements. The high-pressure pump was periodically started using a time-controlled switch to convey liquid reaction mixture through the sample loop. The high pressure pump was operated for about 2 minutes at a flow rate of 12 mL min^{-1} to ensure that the composition of the sample in the loop (or more precisely in the NMR spectrometer) matched the composition of the reaction mixture at that time. Subsequently, the pump was stopped and the sample was left to rest for a period of two minutes, allowing the temperature to reach a steady state. Thereafter, the acquisition of the NMR spectrum was initiated and repeated multiple times (for further details, see Section 3.2). Sufficient exchange of fluid in the sample loop during the flow sequence was validated by previous experiments. The experiments were terminated by deactivating the heater and decreasing the pressure.

For the kinetic studies, this experimental procedure was repeated several times with the reaction temperature and hydrogen pressure being varied. In order to investigate the ageing of the catalyst, the final experiment (5) in the kinetic studies was carried out under precisely the same operation conditions as the first experiment (1).

The exact process conditions including the chosen sampling method, the mean reaction temperature and pressure are summarized in Tab. 3.1.

Table 3.1: Reaction conditions of the experimental runs.

Experiment	Pressure bar	Temperature °C	method
1	7	60	I
2	10	80	I
3	10	60	I
4	7	80	I
5	7	60	I
6	10	80	II

The temperature was continuously monitored throughout all experiments and remained constant during ± 0.5 Kelvin within each experiment. The pressure was also recorded and shown to deviate by only ± 0.03 bar from the set point. For the purposes of this study, these fluctuations were considered negligible and are not expected to have a significant impact on the results.

3.2 NMR Methods and Data Analysis

^1H NMR experiments with ^{13}C decoupling were conducted using a Spinsolve 60 Ultra benchtop spectrometer (Magritek) with a magnetic field strength of 1.46 T resulting in a ^1H Larmor frequency of 62.5 MHz. The minimization of the magnetic field inhomogeneity (shimming) was performed once before each experimental run before the reaction was started using the automatic routines provided by the manufacturer. A pulse sequence available in the manufacturer’s pulse sequence library (1D PROTON CDec) was applied. The ^1H experiments were performed at 26 °C with the following parameters: 3.2 s acquisition time, 90° excitation pulse angle, 16k data points and 8 scans. Repetition time was set to 10 s to ensure that the nuclei were in equilibrium before they were excited again for reliable quantification of all components’ concentration. The longest T_1 time of all components present in the mixture was preliminary determined to be 1.5 s.

Additional high-frequency NMR experiments were performed with a Bruker Biospin Avance III HD 400 operating at 9.4 T field strength and a resulting ^1H Larmor frequency of 400.13 MHz. With this instrument ^{13}C decoupled ^1H experiments as well as additional ^{13}C experiments were conducted at a temperature of 26 °C at a frequency of 400.13 MHz using standard routines provided by the manufacturer. Acquisition time, number of scans and pulse angle were adopted from the experiments conducted with the low frequency spectrometer. In this work, the model-based evaluation tool Q²NMR (version 2.0.1, available from Daniel Holland, University of Canterbury, on request) was used to evaluate proton NMR spectra and is further referred to as QM-qNMR tool. Instead of classical peak integration, the spectrum y is modeled here as a weighted superposition of the signals of different components $z_k(\Theta_k)$

$$y = \sum_{k=1}^{N_{\text{comp, QM}}} b_k z_k(\Theta_k) \quad (3.1)$$

On the one hand, this allows superimposed peaks to be quantified and represents an elegant way of still being able to evaluate spectra with low signal-to-noise ratio reliably [25–27]. The NMR signals of the individual species are described using a model based on quantum mechanics (QM). Details regarding the quantum mechanical formulations and parameters and the fitting algorithm are described in detail in the literature [27, 28, 30, 50]. The strength of this method lies in the fact that the model parameters Θ_k such as chemical shifts and J-couplings are initialized using prior knowledge and do not have to be estimated solely on the basis of the recorded spectra [30]. In this work, these model parameter were obtained from benchtop spectra of the commercially available pure substances MBY, MBE and MBA. Spectra that were acquired during one kinetic experiment were eventually evaluated using the QM-qNMR tool. The spectra were automatically phase and baseline corrected. The prior probability distributions were all assumed to be

uniformly distributed with a standard value, a lower and an upper limit. The fitting routine for subsequent spectra, which were acquired within a kinetic experiment, was greatly accelerated by accessing data from the previous analysis.

Fig. 3.2 shows an example of the model-based analysis of a mixture containing MBY, MBE and MBA including the model predictions of the spectra of the individual components.

Figure 3.2: Example of model-based analysis of the ^1H NMR spectrum of a mixture containing MBY, MBE and MBA. Green, orange and purple areas: model prediction of the contribution of MBY, MBE and MBA to the NMR spectrum of the mixture. Blue line: predicted NMR spectrum obtained by superposition of the spectra of the individual components.

The QM-qNMR provides the mole ratio ζ_i for all components $N_{\text{comp}}^{\text{QM}}$ included in the QM model.

$$\zeta_i = \frac{n_i^{\text{QM}}}{\sum_{k=1}^{N_{\text{comp}}^{\text{QM}}} n_k^{\text{QM}}} \quad (3.2)$$

In this case, it is assumed that the concentration of components not included in the QM-qNMR (i.e., components that have not been elucidated) is negligible. Consequently, the mole ratio ζ_i corresponds to the mole fraction x_i and the concentration of components c_i can be calculated directly from the mole ratio:

$$c_i \approx \frac{\zeta_i}{v_{\text{mix}}^{(n)}} \quad (3.3)$$

Preliminary investigation was conducted to assess the accuracy of the evaluation method. This investigation involved the use of diverse test samples, encompassing a mixture of the three primary components: MBY, MBA, and MBE. The samples were prepared gravimetrically using a balance (see 3.1). The concentration ranges of the three species were selected to correspond to the anticipated concentration range during the reaction. The mole

ratios obtained with the QM-qNMR tool from the acquired spectra of the test samples were compared with the mole fractions known from the gravimetric sample preparation. The results are displayed in the form of parity plots, as illustrated in Fig. 3.3.

Figure 3.3: Comparison of the concentration of the three components as determined from the weighed sample and the concentration as determined by NMR measurement.

The mean absolute deviation of the mole fractions determined with the two methods was $0.0037 \text{ mol mol}^{-1}$, the largest absolute deviation was $0.007 \text{ mol mol}^{-1}$. Quantification with the model-based NMR analysis thus provides sufficiently accurate results for process monitoring using qNMR.

Side product quantification was possible after identifying them and developing a model for them in the QM-qNMR. Therefore dimers had to be present in higher concentration to be subsequently analyzed with a high frequency NMR. Since the dimers are suspected to have a higher boiling point than the components partaking in the main reaction due to the former's higher molar mass, the samples for side-product identification were concentrated in a rotary evaporator (Heidolph Laborota 4000 Efficient). Distillation was carried out at an oil bath temperature of $150 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ under nitrogen inertization. High temperature was necessary to ensure evaporation of light boilers. As no hydrogen or catalyst was present during distillation it is assumed, that no further reactions took place. This was also confirmed by preliminary studies. Dimers known from the literature, as well as other possible dimers, were translated into simulated spectra using a neural network-based prediction tool [51]. Manual spectral pattern recognition using these database-simulated spectra was subsequently applied to the measured spectra. Additional ^{13}C measurements were conducted to confirm the assumed compounds. Parameters for the most frequently found dimers were added to the QM-qNMR tool, adjusting the fit parameters in an iterative process to optimally replicate the measured spectrum. By subsequently applying the parameters of the experimental reaction mixture, quantification of dimeric side products' concentration is possible (see Sec. (4.2)).

3.2.1 Estimation of Kinetic Parameters

The component balance equations (Eq. (2.6) - Eq. (2.8)) form a system of ordinary differential equations (ODEs). In this work, the kinetic parameters (see equations Eq. (2.1)) and Eq. (2.2)) were not adopted from the literature, but rather, were estimated using the measured concentration profiles. The parameters were estimated by solving the ODEs numerically and minimizing the error between the model predictions and the measured concentrations. The objective function of this optimization is shown in Eq. (3.4). The function `lsqnonlin` of the Optimization Toolbox (version 9.5) in Matlab (version 9.14.0.2206163) was used to solve this problem.

$$k_I, k_{II}, K_i = \arg \min_{k_I, k_{II}, K_i} \sum_{k=1}^{n_{\text{sample}}} \sum_{i=1}^{N_{\text{comp}}} (\zeta_{i,k}^{\text{obs}} - \zeta_i^{\text{model}}(t_k, k_I, k_{II}, K_i, a, V_1, T, p, c_{\text{H}_2}(T, p), n_{\text{pd}}))^2 \quad (3.4)$$

$$i = \{1 \text{ for MBY, } 2 \text{ for MBE, } 3 \text{ for Hydrogen}\}$$

$$k = 1 \dots n_{\text{sample}}$$

The parameters k_I , k_{II} , K_{MBY} , K_{MBE} and K_{H_2} were fitted for each experiment individually. The reaction conditions were either specified by the experiment (T , p , n_{pd} , V_1) or calculated from models Eq. (2.4) and Eq. (2.5)) in case of c_{H_2} and a .

The parameters were estimated to ascertain the extent to which the experimental data can be described with the kinetics approach from the literature. The primary objective was to demonstrate the consistency of the experimental data and the adequacy of the experimental methodology for determining reaction kinetics. The target of this study was not to develop a comprehensive and universally valid kinetics model.

4 Results and Discussion

4.1 Main Reaction Parameter Studies

All hydrogenation samples were quantified using the previously determined parameters of the QM-qNMR tool in order to separate overlapping peaks, as illustrated in Fig. 3.2, initially disregarding side-products.

Fig. 4.1 shows the stacked spectra of a fully automated hydrogenation experiment using the online monitoring setup (method II).

Figure 4.1: Stacked ¹H-NMR spectra of the reaction mixture during hydrogenation at 10 bar and 80 °C automatically monitored online with benchtop NMR for 10 hours.

Each individual spectrum was analyzed fully automatically by the QM-qNMR evaluation

tool without any further modification of the fitting routine once set, making data evaluation very convenient. As illustrated in Figure Fig. 4.2, the resulting profile of the relative molar fraction during the hydrogenation experiment conducted at 10 bar pressure and a temperature of 80 °C is displayed.

Figure 4.2: Concentration profiles of the main components during hydrogenation experiments at 10 bar and 80 °C. The concentrations were obtained from ¹H-NMR spectra recorded with 60 MHz benchtop NMR and analyzed using the QM-qNMR tool. The samples were taken automatically. Symbols: Experimental Data.

The high temporal resolution of the data points, which was achieved by analyzing 70 samples during a single experiment, enables the extraction of qualitative conclusions and corroborates the hypothesized kinetics. It is imperative to acknowledge the challenges associated with classical sampling at this frequency and over such an extended period in routine laboratory settings. It is estimated that approximately 60 % of the reaction mixture would be lost if withdrawn from the vessel, thereby altering the catalyst-to-reactant ratio and impeding a meaningful evaluation of the temporal concentration profile. This is a factor that must be given due consideration in the context of model studies.

The concave decline of the relative molar fraction of MBY from $t = 0 \text{ min}$ to $t = 170 \text{ min}$ underscores the hypothesis of an underlying catalyst inhibition by MBY, as previously documented in literature [34–36]. The formation of the successive product MBA from MBE increases significantly only upon nearly full conversion of the reactant MBY and its relative molar ratio drops below 0.1 mol/mol, substantiating the high selectivity of the Pd-catalyst for the formation of MBE. The molar fraction of the secondary product remains below 0.04 mol/mol until concentration of MBY has dropped below 0.1 mol/mol. The precise identification of the sharp optimum in the yield was only possible because

of the high density of data points. The graph reveals the absence of significant outliers, with profiles aligning closely with data presented in literature. Consequently, the efficacy of the employed NMR method in mapping the progression of the reaction is confirmed, yielding consistent results. It has been observed that the presence of MBY in the reaction mixture results in the predominant formation of MBE as the primary product.

Given the employment of the same sample of catalyst for all experimental runs without regeneration, it can be deduced that catalyst deactivation transpired over the course of the series of experiments. This hypothesis is corroborated by a later repetition of a hydrogenation experiment from the start of this study, under identical reaction conditions. Fig. 4.3 presents the comparison of the concentration profiles of two hydrogenation experiments with fresh catalyst (1) and used catalyst (2) both conducted at 7 bar and 60 °C.

Figure 4.3: Concentration profiles of MBY and MBE during two separate hydrogenation experiments at 7 bar and 60 °C. The concentrations were obtained from ¹H-NMR spectra recorded with a 60 MHz benchtop NMR instrument and analyzed using the QM-qNMR tool with catalyst in operation for 14 hours (1) and 60 hours (2), respectively. The samples were taken manually. Symbols: Experimental data. Lines: Model predictions.

It is evident that, under identical reaction conditions, the reaction rate of the initial experiment that employed catalyst already used for 14 h (1) is decreased by 13 % in a subsequent experiment that uses the same catalyst after an operation time of 60 h (2). The deactivation of the catalyst has therefore to be taken into account in the model using Eq. (2.5).

The kinetic model was fitted to the experimental data using the parameter estimation procedure introduced in Sec. (3.2.1). Fig. 4.4 presents a comparison between the experi-

mental data and the model prediction.

Figure 4.4: Concentration profiles of the main components during hydrogenation experiments at 10 bar and 80 °C. The concentrations were obtained from ¹H-NMR spectra recorded with 60 MHz benchtop NMR instrument and analyzed using QM-qNMR. The samples were taken manually. Symbols: Experimental data. Lines: Model predictions.

In this experiment, the manual sampling method was employed, resulting in a reduced number of data points in Fig. 4.2 compared to the experiment shown in Fig. 4.4. A qualitative comparison of the concentration profiles obtained with the two different sampling methods supports the conclusion that the quality of parameter estimation is sufficient for the study's purposes, even with fewer data points. Moreover, the comparison of the experimental data with the model prediction reveals a good level of agreement. This finding demonstrates that the experimental method consistently generates data that align with the reaction stoichiometry and can be adequately described by the model.

The influence of hydrogen pressure and reaction temperature on the course of the consumption of MBY and production of MBE is shown in Fig. 4.5 and Fig. 4.6 respectively.

Figure 4.5: Concentration profiles of MBY during hydrogenation experiments at 7 and 10 bar and 60 and 80 °C. The concentrations were obtained from ^1H -NMR spectra recorded with 60 MHz benchtop NMR instrument and analyzed using QM-qNMR. The samples were taken manually. Symbols: Experimental data. Lines: Model predictions.

Figure 4.6: Concentration profiles of MBE during hydrogenation experiments at 7 and 10 bar and 60 and 80 °C. The concentrations were obtained from ^1H -NMR spectra recorded with 60 MHz benchtop NMR instrument and analyzed using QM-qNMR. The samples were taken manually. Symbols: Experimental data. Lines: Model predictions.

It is evident that both pressure and temperature have a significant impact on the reaction rate. 50 % conversion of MBY is achieved more than twice as fast at 10 bar and 80 °C

compared to 60 °C, while at 7 bar, it is about 1.5 times faster. The influence of pressure is more pronounced at higher temperatures than at lower temperatures. Sensitivities with regard to the reaction parameters appear in Fig. 4.5 and Fig. 4.6 as they would have been expected from the literature results and correspond to expectations. The parameter studies show therefore internally consistent results and lead to the reaction constants summarized in Tab. 4.1.

Table 4.1: Parameters of the kinetic models.

Parameter	Unit	T	80 °C	80 °C	60 °C	60 °C
		p	10 bar	7 bar	10 bar	7 bar
k_1	mol/(s mol _{Pd})		$9.144 \cdot 10^3$	$9.917 \cdot 10^3$	$4.120 \cdot 10^3$	$5.962 \cdot 10^3$
k_2	mol/(s mol _{Pd})		$1.234 \cdot 10^5$	$1.600 \cdot 10^5$	$7.049 \cdot 10^4$	$1.807 \cdot 10^5$
K_{MBY}	m ³ /mol		$1.477 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$1.083 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$1.130 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$1.015 \cdot 10^{-2}$
K_{MBE}	m ³ /mol		$5.448 \cdot 10^{-7}$	$7.554 \cdot 10^{-7}$	$4.823 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$2.511 \cdot 10^{-5}$
K_{H_2}	m ³ /mol		$8.689 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$5.961 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$6.502 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$5.238 \cdot 10^{-4}$
MSE	(mol/mol) ²		$2.016 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$8.815 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$3.403 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$7.326 \cdot 10^{-5}$

Reaction monitoring using Benchtop NMR combined with the QM-qNMR method thus proved to be suitable for the investigated system in order to carry out detailed parameter studies.

4.2 Elucidation and Quantification of side-products.

Figure 4.7 presents the complete measured spectrum of a sample withdrawn from a hydrogenation experiment with the fitted individual signals of the main components, as well as magnified sections.

Figure 4.7: ^1H NMR spectrum of a sample from the hydrogenation experiment at 7 bar and 80°C measured with the 60 MHz benchtop NMR spectrometer (top) and the high-frequency NMR spectrometer (bottom).

In the 60 MHz NMR spectrum, identifying the side products is particularly challenging due to lower resolution, broader peaks, and as a consequence increased overlap. In contrast, the magnified view of the high-frequency NMR measurement reveals distinct peaks and multiplet structures. The region between 1.5 and 2.5 ppm is not examined in detail due to the overlap of methyl group peaks from different components; however, additional peaks are observed here that cannot be attributed to the main components. Additional high-frequency ^1H as well as ^{13}C spectra were evaluated. As shown in Fig. 4.8, the observed peaks and multiplet structures were compared with predictions. Due to impurities present, evaluation of the dimers only present in very low concentrations was qualitative only.

Figure 4.8: High frequency ^{13}C NMR Spectrum of concentrated reaction product mixture of a hydrogenation experiment with spectra of suspected dimers predicted in MestreNova. Highlighted regions corresponding to characteristic peaks of those compounds.

The peaks assumed to represent dimeric compounds were found to correspond to 2,7-dimethyl-3,5-octadiene-2,7-diol and the subsequent hydrogenation products 2,7-dimethyl-3-octene-2,7-diol and 2,7-octane-2,7-diol (see Fig. 2.1). Dimeric alkynols in significant quantities were not be found. Consequently, the formation of dimers by reductive dimerization, i.e. the pathway illustrated in Fig. 2.1, emerges as a highly probable reaction pathway [37–41]. This finding is consistent with the present reaction conditions of hydrogenation, as reductive dimerization is favored. Although this purely qualitative comparative approach can only provide a rough estimate of possible reaction mechanisms, it is

significantly simpler in terms of time and preparation than classical structure elucidation, as the presence of numerous interfering components in the reaction mixture in addition of the molecules of interest and large concentration differences between the components present in the sample prevented reliable structural elucidation using 2D NMR techniques. Studies aimed at improving the procedure and enabling structure elucidation during the course of a hydrogenation experiment using 2D NMR methods are currently underway. The application of a 400-MHz spectrometer and the analysis of the spectrum in (Fig. 4.7) were indispensable for arriving at this conclusion. QM-qNMR was instrumental in analyzing the spectrum as even in the high-frequency NMR spectrum peak overlapping occurred.

Spectral data of dimers identified can now be included as prior knowledge to quantify the relative molar fraction of dimers in spectra recorded with the benchtop spectrometer. In the ensuing discussion, the mole fraction of the individual dimer species is not addressed. Rather, all dimer species are aggregated to form a collective mole fraction of dimers for the single concentrations being too low to allow a meaningful representation. Given that all dimers are regarded as undesirable byproducts, this simplification is deemed acceptable for the purpose of investigating the impact of operational conditions on byproduct formation.

Figure 4.9: Concentration profiles of the main components and dimers during hydrogenation experiments at 10 bar and 80 °C. The concentrations were obtained from ¹H-NMR spectra recorded with 60 MHz benchtop NMR and analyzed using QM-qNMR. The samples were taken manually. Symbols: Experimental data. Solid Lines: Model predictions. Dashed line: Guide to the eye.

The molar fraction of the side products found is two orders of magnitude lower than that of the main components. The simplification made in Eq. (3.3), where only the relative molar proportions of the main components are taken into account in the calculation, is therefore valid. Although the amounts of dimers present are very small especially in comparison with impurities present in the used reactant, it is possible to quantify them. The data are consistent and in agreement with the results expected from the reaction mechanism.

The QM-qNMR approach is also robust to dimer formation and provides reliable data. Thus, the QM-qNMR method is also well suited for use in reaction engineering parameter studies of dimer formation. The results of studies conducted are shown in Fig. 4.10 and Fig. 4.11.

Figure 4.10: Concentration profiles of the main components and dimers during hydrogenation experiments at 10 bar and 80 °C. The concentrations were obtained from $^1\text{H-NMR}$ spectra recorded with 60 MHz benchtop NMR instrument and analyzed using QM-qNMR. The samples were taken manually. Symbols: Experimental data. Dashed line: Guide to the eye.

The concentration profiles of the formed dimers (see Fig. 4.10) show a direct dependence of dimer formation on pressure and temperature during hydrogenation. The data are consistent and do not qualitatively deviate from the expected trends. The influence of pressure and temperature on the rate of formation is consistent with the trends to be expected for reductive dimerisation. It can be stated that higher reaction temperatures and greater hydrogen availability for the reaction will speed up the formation of dimers. The influence in question is analogous to that which has been observed on product formation during the primary reaction. In Fig. 4.11, the correlation between the extent of the dimerization reactions and the conversion of MBY is shown.

Figure 4.11: Concentration profile of dimers during hydrogenation experiments at 7 and 10 bar and 60 and 80 °C as a function of MBY conversion. The concentrations were obtained from ¹H-NMR spectra recorded with 60 MHz benchtop NMR instrument and analyzed using QM-qNMR. The samples were taken manually. Symbols: Experimental data. Dashed line: Guide to the eye.

In this analysis, the reaction profiles across all experiments are nearly identical, indicating that the reaction conditions have little influence on dimer formation and, consequently, on the yield of the target product. Our findings demonstrate a direct correlation between dimerization and the conversion of MBY. It is evident that utilising an identical catalyst and manipulating solely the parameters of pressure and temperature exerts negligible impact on the formation of undesirable side products. Consequently, subsequent optimisation of the process must be predicated on disparate parameters. The quantification of the formed dimers by means of QM-qNMR Benchtop NMR can be applied without restriction to the reaction system under consideration. It is possible to obtain consistent and meaningful quantitative data with little apparatus effort, even for substances that only occur in low concentrations. The parameter studies of the reaction engineering could be extended by adding additional prior knowledge. The results shown here are the best compromise between additional knowledge gained and analytical effort.

5 Conclusions

In this study, we investigated the hydrogenation of 2-methyl-3-butyn-2-ol (MBY) under various reaction conditions. We successfully utilized benchtop nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectroscopy in conjunction with a model-based quantitative evaluation tool. The challenge of integration of overlapping peaks in NMR spectra could be conveniently resolved by applying the QM-qNMR tool, thereby demonstrating that previously generally accepted weaknesses of benchtop NMR spectrometers do no longer have to be accepted. This approach was found to be suitable for the effective quantification of primary components. The presented approach is particularly beneficial when evaluating numerous similar spectra, as in kinetic parameter studies. The kinetic parameters derived from these experiments are consistent with those reported in the existing literature, thereby validating the reliability of the methodology employed. Furthermore, the experimental results not only corroborate the suspicions raised in the literature regarding the reaction, but also provide evidence of catalyst deactivation effects.

High-frequency NMR remains indispensable for detailed structural elucidation, while the benchtop NMR measurements conducted in this study have allowed to monitor formation of multiple secondary components during the reaction, some of which undergo further transformations. Incorporating this prior knowledge in the QM-qNMR model allows for refinement of our model, facilitating the quantification of these dimers. These dimers likely form through direct reductive dimerization, implicating hydrogen in side-product formation. For the monitoring of reactions under varying conditions, even approximate assessments of side-product formation are valuable.

While the formation rate of both dimers and target products was influenced by temperature and pressure, the final amount of dimer formed was independent of these parameters, thereby limiting their effectiveness in improving selectivity and yield. For the studied catalyst, it can therefore be stated that a change in the basic process parameters alone has no influence on minimizing the formation of side-products.

A more precise analysis of the side-products necessitates further experimentation and chemical structure elucidation, such as two-dimensional NMR measurements.

The QM-qNMR quantification required prior knowledge of potential components, and the accuracy was enhanced through the use of preliminary experiments to refine the spectral

model. The incorporation of prior knowledge about the chemical shift was found to improve the correlation between estimated and actual concentrations, and to facilitate automated analysis of the reaction mixtures. It has been shown that this system offers broad adaptability and can be customized to meet specific requirements, with the balance between equipment complexity, such as automation, and the depth of information gained being able to be tailored to future needs, thereby promoting an efficient and streamlined experimental design. The integration of benchtop NMR spectroscopy with an advanced quantum-mechanical analysis tool demonstrates significant potential for application in industrial reaction engineering laboratories.

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